

Business Process as a Service (BPaaS): A Model-Based Approach for Smart Business and IT-Cloud Alignment

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Abstract.

The use of cloud computing for the benefit of business is an ambitious goal considering the gap between domain-oriented business processes and executable workflows within a Cloud environment.

This tutorial teaches a model based approach, where (a) business process specify the domain, (b) workflow models are used to orchestrate cloud offerings, (c) decision models are used for cloud infrastructure adaptations and (d) ontologies are used to semantically glue all parts together.

Such a model-based approach enables both, (i) human oriented knowledge technologies and (ii) machine oriented knowledge technologies for a hybrid knowledge processing.

This tutorial targets the practical use, the adaptation and implementation of aforementioned model-based knowledge processing and hence targets cloud brokers. These are limited by current “off the shelf” solutions that focus on delivering virtual server, but do not offer the possibility to “re-implement” individualized solution from scratch on a more business oriented level. Hence this tutorial provides initial solutions use but focuses on the adaptation, extension and re-implementation features of the enabling meta-modelling platform. The audience gets introduced into one of the leading meta-modelling platforms called ADOxx, in form of the world-wide active adoxx.org community, which provides tutorials and training in different application domains.

1 Intended Audience

Participants with business informatics, mathematical or system modelling background that are well familiar with concept modelling are addressed by the open available meta modelling platform providing a set of pragmatically usable solutions to realize knowledge processing.

Participants with technical informatics, service and software engineering as well as with workflow background those are familiar with distributed systems. This tutorial addresses the limitations of existing cloud offerings and in particular how multi cloud

deployment can be addressed by introducing meta modelling as a technology to enable smart any hybrid knowledge processing.

2 Learning Outcome

Participants will understand the current gaps between business level processes and current cloud offerings. They will be able to name that major challenges for providing a Business Process as a Service (BPaaS) layer on top of current Cloud offerings and why a meta modeling approach is a potential solution. Following the course participants will be able to name the basic properties and benefits of meta modelling technology and will be able to assess its capabilities and limitations for introducing smart knowledge techniques into the cloud computing domain. Course participants will have a basic understanding of the modeling approach of Clouds and how it can be applied to selected application scenarios. Participants will be able to apply the principle to other scenarios and solutions. In the particular field of business and IT-Cloud alignment, participants will understand the concept and will learn how to transfer and apply their knowledge to new scenarios immediately after the tutorial. Participants get familiar with the ADOxx.org community consisting of more than 500 developers, collaborating with five research laboratories and about 15 cooperating Universities.

3 Description

3.1 Business Process as a Service

The first part of the tutorial focuses on Business Process as a Service (BPaaS) [1] and requirements to smartly bridge business domain requirements to cloud-based IT solutions. The different model-based representations and requirements to smartly interpret those models are presented and requirements for the next sessions are collected.

This part starts with an overview of the underpinning architecture of current Cloud offerings using the Open Source solution OpenStack. Based on this in particular the gap between current Cloud offerings and the business process level is shown along an example business process. The notion of Business Process as a Service (BPaaS) as an extension of the existing layered model of IaaS, PaaS, SaaS is introduced and defined. Furthermore the challenges of such a layer and the gap between current offerings and this layer are introduced. This part concludes with derived requirements and key properties of a solution and motivates why a meta-modelling based approach is a potential solution [2].

3.2 Sample Solutions and Implementation

The second tutorial session introduces how an initial modelling tool for BPaaS that has been implemented with ADOxx [3], [4] addresses aforementioned concerns by providing solutions for (a) business process modelling [5] with BPMN

2.0 [6], (b) Executable workflow modelling [7] with BPMN, (c) decision and rule modelling with DMN [8] and (d) semantic annotation using RDFS [9], [10].

Aforementioned sample business process will be demonstrated in BPMN and bridging mechanisms to a workflow – also expressed in BPMN – will be elaborated by (i) introduction of additional modelling aspects – such as (a) intermediate layers that describe functional capabilities of the expected cloud offerings and (b) introduce the corresponding human collaboration (b1) via this intermediate model layer, (b2) using an external Wiki tool, (b3) collaboration features in the models or (b4) alerting mechanisms to inform other users; (ii) semantic lifting by annotating ontological concept that describe the business and IT alignment either by direct textual annotation, the integration of ontological third party systems or a hybrid solution of semantic lifting.

This part provides modeling tool prototypes in form of modelling languages and scripts, which can be used, adapted or extended during or after the tutorial. Different implementation variations will be discussed with the participants to support future development decisions of the participants.

3.3 Meta Modelling Foundations and Community Entry Points

The last part of the tutorial introduces the theoretical principles behind meta-modelling tool development and it demonstrates relevant concepts of a meta-modelling platform in general and of the development platform ADOxx in particular. Beside the foundations on modelling methods [11] and the underlying Generic Modelling Method Specification Framework [12], the principles of adapting the modelling language and implementing corresponding functionality are explained to provide an outlook to the participants, how they can use aforementioned solutions to create their own business and IT-cloud alignment modelling tool. The challenges of hybrid modelling, semantic lifting or collaborative modelling [13] using add-on implementation are elaborated and relevant entry points to the communities and to the portals are provided, so participants know how to participate the development community [14].

4 Previous Tutorials and novel character:

The ADOxx.org [3] community started 2012 with a tutorial in conjunction with a workshop of the Open Models [12] community in Vienna. Since then, knowledge from one of the most successful commercial modelling platforms – ADOxx – into an open platform for researcher has been transformed in a series of trainings, tutorials and publications.

Hence a series of tutorials at conferences teach the meta modelling aspects like:

- “T13-Developing modelling toolkits for requirements engineering” at 22nd IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference, Karlskrona, Sweden, 26.08.2014 [15]

- “Conceptual Model Value Creation with ADOxx” at PoEM 2013, Practice of Enterprise Modeling; Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia, 06.-07.11.2013 [16]
- “Meta-modelling: Operationalizing modeling methods with ADOxx”, Informatik 2013, Universität Koblenz-Landau, Germany, 16.-20.09.2013 [17]
- “Value Creation through Concept Models”, 12th IFIP Conference on e-Business, e-Service, e-Society I3E 2013, Athens, Greece, 25.-26.04.2013 [18]
- “From Model Editors to Modelling Tools: Operationalizing Modelling Methods with ADOxx”, ACM/IEEE 15th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages & Systems MODELS 2012, Innsbruck, Austria, 01.10.2012 [19]
- “ADOxx Tutorial”, 3rd International Workshop of the Open Models Initiative "Modelling Methods in Motion", Vienna, Austria, 13.09.2012 [20]

In addition to those tutorials in conjunction with conferences regular training days are organized and published at [21].

Novel character of this tutorial in comparison with the previous is that meta modeling technology is applied in the domain of business and IT-alignment with special focus on cloud computing. In particular the use of decision models for flexible cloud infrastructure management is a novel aspect,

5 Provided Material and Teaching Methods and

Interactive presentations will be used for the theoretical parts and live demonstrations for the practical parts. Workshop-like discussions are continuously initiated to collect participant’s expectations, raise attention and receive feedback.

Participants are encouraged to download material to enhance their tutorial experience. These include: (a) ADOxx development platform, (b) BPaaS samples and documentation from the CloudSocket development space (c) entry points to the ADOxx.org community.

Material is available for participants before, during and after the tutorial. Each participant will get an account on ADOxx.org to develop their own modelling toolkit. Material is available at: www.adoxx.org.

This tutorial will be promoted within the ADOxx.org community consisting of 500 developers and 1.800 interested stakeholders.

6 Short CV of Presenters

Stefan Wesner is the director of the Communication and Information Centre (KIZ) and the institute for Organization and Management of Information systems (IOMI) of the University of Ulm. Furthermore he is the scientific chairman of the research network ISP BelWü connecting the 9 state universities and 40 applied research schools in the region. He has been actively participating in research projects on

national and international level since 1997, focusing in particular on distributed systems and improving programmability and usability of large scale systems.

Jörg Domschka is senior researcher at IOMI since May 2013. He has been working in European research projects since 2006 and is actively involved in the PaaSage and the CloudSocket project as well as CACTOS where he holds the position of a project manager. He holds a PhD in computer science from University of Ulm, and his current research interests include fault-tolerance in distributed environments, self-adaptability and scalability, as well as cloud-enabling programming paradigms and cloud-enabled application architectures.

Robert Woitsch is managing director and responsible for open innovation at BOC. He holds a PhD in business informatics and was and is involved in commercial and European projects dealing with conceptual modeling as a cross-domain issue since fifteen years. He has practical experiences of more than twenty EU projects concerned with the conceptualizations of meta-models. Recently his group started to host the adoxx.org open platform.

Wilfrid Utz is a PhD student at the Knowledge Engineering research group of the University of Vienna on the realization approach for domain-specific modeling methods applying meta-modeling concepts and is working for the BOC research and development team since September 2004. He holds an MSc in international business administration with a focus on business informatics. He was responsible for the development of modeling tools in more than fifteen EU projects and supported several projects from the Open Model Laboratory.

7 Requested Length of Tutorial

Half Day Tutorial

8 References

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